

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF THE BEHAVIOR OF DUAL FIBRE HYBRID COMPOSITES UNDER DIFFERENT STACKING SEQUENCES

Dr. K. M. Gupta

Professor, Department of Applied Mechanics,
Motilal Nehru National Institute of Technology (Deemed University),
Allahabad – 211004, INDIA.

E-mail: kmgupta@mnnit.ac.in, kmgupta1948@indiatimes.com

SUMMARY

Composites made of natural fibres are cheaper, eco-friendly and lighter in weight; but their strength is lower than the composites made of synthetic fibres. Hence for optimum utilization of light weightness and strength, a polymeric hybrid composite having two different kinds of fibres has been developed in this investigation. The material system consists of natural flax fibre, synthetic glass fibre and epoxy polymer. Consequently, the flax fibre reinforced composite (FFRC) lamina and glass fibre reinforced composite (GRP) lamina have been fabricated. The hybridization of these laminae has been done in two different stacking sequences viz. GRP lamina sandwiched between FFRC laminae, and FFRC lamina sandwiched between GRP laminae. The two kinds of hybrids thus produced are named as glass-flax-glass-hybrid (GFGH) and flax-glass-flax-hybrid (FGFH). Their static behaviour under tension, compression, bending and impact loadings have been investigated by conducting experiments using strain gauge rosette technology. The stress-strain curves and load-deflection characteristics are obtained. The tensile, compressive, flexure and impact strengths; and specific strength have been calculated. Various strengths and specific strength of hybrid composite has considerably increased due to hybridization and stacking sequences. Based on the findings of the experimental results, it is concluded that the selection of stacking sequence of laminae in a hybrid composite plays a vital role in achieving favourable mechanical properties.

Keywords: Dual fibre hybrid, Different stacking sequence, Glass-flax-glass fibre hybrid, Flax-glass-flax fibre hybrid, Mechanical characterization, Effect of stacking sequence

1. INTRODUCTION

Composites made of conventional fibres have a high cost. If made of cheaper fibres, they will cut-down the cost of components for which they are used. Natural fibres are such materials. They are not only cheap, but are abundantly available also. They possess high specific strength and low specific weight, and are ecologically favourable too. However, their strength is not as high as those of synthetic fibres. Hence, if natural

fibre composites are made hybrid with synthetic fibre composites, the resulting hybrid composite is likely to be a blend of lightweight and strong material. The present work has been undertaken with this aim. One fibre is natural and the other is synthetic. The natural fibre is of flax (Fig. 1), while the synthetic fibre is of glass (Fig. 2).

Fig 1. Natural flax fibre

Fig 2. Synthetic glass fibre

2. FABRICATION OF COMPOSITES AND HYBRID

In this work, a unidirectional (U/D) flax fibre reinforced composite (FFRC) and a U/D glass fibre reinforced composite (GRP) have been fabricated [1] using hand lay-up process. Epoxy (Araldite AY-103) has been used as matrix constituent. The hybrid is made of two different composite laminae viz. flax polymer composite and glass fibre composite. They have been stacked in two different sequences as shown in Figs. 3 and 4. Laminae of both of these composites are glued alternately to produce glass-flax-glass-hybrid (GFGH) and flax-glass-flax-hybrid (FGFH). A unidirectional FFRC sheet has been prepared by laying successive layers of araldite and flax fibre. Mylar sheet has been used on inner surfaces of the mould for a better surface finish and easy withdrawal of composite. Heavy weights are hung on both sides of the fibres to maintain unidirectionality in it. Metal roller has been rolled over each layer to remove entrapped air, if any.

Fig. 3 Glass-flax-glass fibre hybrid (GFGH) epoxy plastic

Fig. 4 Flax-glass-flax fibre hybrid (FGFH) epoxy plastic

3. TESTING OF COMPOSITES AND HYBRIDS

Specimens of FFRC, GRP, GFGH and FGFH composites have been prepared and tested under tension, compression, bending and impact to characterize their properties. The testings have been done in accordance with Indian Standards. The tensile test has been performed on Hounsfield Tensometer (Fig. 5), the compression test on Universal Testing machine, the bending test on Hounsfield Tensometer using the bending attachment, and impact test on Izod impact testing machine. Their details follow in subsequent sections.

Fig. 5 The experimental set-up showing the Hounsfield Tensometer, tensile test specimen, and strain gauge indicator

4. TESTING OF FLAX FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE (FFRC)

The flax fibres used are 300 mm in length. Density of the composite has been determined by measuring its weight and volume, and is found to be 1648 kg/m^3 .

4.1 Tensile Testing

Tensile testing has been performed on the specimens having volume fraction of fibres $V_f \approx 54\%$ in accordance with Indian Standard. The rectangular specimen is of 16 mm x 3 mm cross-section, overall length = 150 mm, and gauge length = 28 mm. The specimen sustained a maximum load of 150 kg (1500N) and underwent an elongation of 0.14 mm. The observations are taken at a load interval of 10 kg. Thus the ultimate strength is calculated as 312.5 kg/cm^2 (31.25 MPa), linear strain = 5130×10^{-6} , and lateral strain = 4190×10^{-6} . The stress-strain curve is shown in Fig 6.

Fig. 6 Tensile stress-strain curves of FFRC, GRP, GFGH and FGFH.

4.2 Compression Test

This test has been performed on the specimen having flax volume fraction of $V_f \approx 54\%$. The test has been conducted on UTM. The specimen used is of 25 mm x 25 mm cross-

section and 30 mm height. The specimen sustained a maximum load of 1.95 tonne before fracture, where the contraction recorded is 0.18 mm. Thus the ultimate strength is found to be 320 kg/cm² (32 MPa) and linear strain = 6050 x 10⁻⁶. The stress-strain diagram is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Compressive stress-strain curves of FFRC, GRP, GFGH and FGFH.

4.3 Bending Test

This test has been performed on a U/D specimen of $V_{fl} \approx 54\%$. The specimen is of 70 mm span, 20 mm x 3 mm cross-section, simply supported, and subjected to a concentrated mid-span load. The flexure strength is calculated to be 40.8 MPa. Maximum deflection is recorded as 5.1 mm under a load of 70 kg (700N). The load-deflection curve is shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8 Load-deflection curves of FFRC, GRP, GFGH and FGFH in bending

4.4 Impact Test

This test has been performed on a U/D specimen having $V_{fl} \approx 54\%$. The Charpy and Izod tests have been performed on specimens of width = 10 mm and thickness = 10 mm, having depth of v-notch = 2 mm. The length of specimen in Charpy test is 50 mm, while in Izod test it is 75 mm. The impact strength in Charpy test is found to be 0.9 kgm (9 Nm), while in Izod test it is 0.4 kgm (4 Nm).

5. TESTING OF GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE (GRP)

A unidirectional GRP sheet has been prepared by laying successive layers of araldite and glass fibres. Glass fibres used are 300 mm in length. Density of the composite has been determined by measuring its weight and volume, and is found to be 1898 kg/m^3 .

5.1 Tensile Testing

Tensile testing has been performed on the specimens having volume fraction of glass fibres as $V_g \approx 59\%$ in accordance with Indian Standard. The rectangular specimen is of $16 \text{ mm} \times 3 \text{ mm}$ cross-section, overall length = 150 mm, and gauge length = 40 mm. The specimen sustained a maximum load of 150 kg (1500N) and underwent an elongation of 1.0 mm. Thus the ultimate strength is calculated as 333.3 kg/cm^2 (33.3 MPa), linear strain = 6750×10^{-6} and lateral strain = 4780×10^{-6} . The stress-strain curve is shown in Fig 6.

5.2 Compression Test

This test has been performed on the specimen having glass fibre volume fraction of $V_g \approx 59\%$. The specimen used is of $25 \text{ mm} \times 25 \text{ mm}$ cross-section and 30 mm height. The specimen sustained a maximum load of 1.95 tonne before fracture, where the contraction recorded is 0.17 mm. Thus the ultimate strength is found to be 312.3 kg/cm^2 (31.2 MPa) and linear strain = 5710×10^{-6} . The stress-strain diagram is shown in Fig. 7.

5.3 Bending Test

This test has been performed on a U/D specimen of $V_g \approx 59\%$. The specimen is of 70 mm span, $20 \text{ mm} \times 3 \text{ mm}$ cross-section, simply supported, and subjected to a concentrated mid-span load. The flexure strength is found to be 48.2 MPa. Maximum deflection is recorded as 3.6 mm under a load of 110 kg (1100 N). The load-deflection curve is shown in Fig. 8.

5.4 Impact Test

This test has been performed on a U/D specimen having $V_g \approx 59\%$. The Charpy and Izod tests have been performed on specimens of width = 10 mm and thickness = 10 mm, having depth of V-notch = 2 mm. The length of specimen in Charpy test is 50 mm, while in Izod test it is 75 mm. The impact strength in Charpy test is found to be 12 kgm (120 Nm), while in Izod test it is 5.8 kgm (58 Nm).

6. TESTING OF FLAX-GLASS-FLAX FIBRE REINFORCED HYBRID (FGFH)

A unidirectional FGFH sheet has been prepared by laying successive layers of FFRC and GRP sheets glued with araldite. Mylar sheet has been used on inner surfaces of the mould for easy withdrawal of hybrid. Epoxy resin has been sprayed on bottom side of mould and then glass fibres are placed unidirectionally. Metal roller has been rolled over each layer to remove entrapped air, if any, between the layers. The hybrid produced has 3 plies of 14 mm thick, consisting of a ply of GRP sandwiched between two plies of FFRP. Density of the hybrid composite has been determined by measuring its weight and volume, and is found to be 1880 kg/m^3 .

6.1 Tensile Testing

Tensile testing has been performed on the specimens in accordance with Indian Standard. The rectangular specimen is of 14 mm x 24.5 mm cross-section, overall length = 270 mm, and gauge length = 168 mm. The specimen sustained a maximum load of 640 kg (6400 N) and underwent an elongation of 0.68 mm. The observations are taken at load interval of 40 kg. Thus the ultimate strength is calculated as 186.5 kg/cm^2 (18.6 MPa), linear strain = 3780×10^{-6} , and lateral strain = 3580×10^{-6} . The stress-strain curve is shown in Fig 6.

6.2 Compression Test

This test has been performed on the U/D hybrid specimen on UTM. The specimen used is of 25 mm x 25 mm cross-section and 30 mm height. The specimen sustained a maximum load of 3.2 tonnes before fracture, where the contraction recorded is 0.14 mm. Thus the ultimate strength is found to be 512 kg/cm^2 (51.2 MPa) and strain = 4700×10^{-6} . The stress-strain diagram is shown in Fig. 7.

6.3 Bending Test

This test has been performed on a U/D specimen of 270 mm span, 20 mm x 14 mm cross-section, simply supported, and subjected to a concentrated mid-span load. The flexure strength is found to be 309.9 MPa. Maximum deflection is recorded as 3.8 mm under a load of 300.0 kg (3000N). The load-deflection curve is shown in Fig. 8.

6.4 Impact Test

The Charpy and Izod tests have been performed on U/D specimens of width = 10 mm and thickness = 30 mm, having depth of v-notch = 2 mm. The length of specimen in Charpy test is 50 mm, while in Izod test it is 75 mm. The impact strength in Charpy test is found to be 48 kgm (480 Nm), while in Izod test it is 16 kgm (160 Nm).

7. TESTING OF GLASS-FLAX-GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED HYBRID (GFGH)

A unidirectional GFGH sheet has been prepared by laying successive layers of FFRC and GRP sheets glued with araldite. Mylar sheet has been used on inner surfaces of the mould for easy withdrawal of hybrid. Epoxy resin has been sprayed on bottom side of mould and then glass fibres are placed unidirectionally. Metal roller has been rolled over each layer to remove entrapped air, if any, between the layers. The hybrid produced has 3 plies of 14 mm thick, consisting of a ply of FFRC sandwiched between two plies of GRP. Density of the hybrid composite has been determined by measuring its weight and volume, and is found to be 1940 kg/m^3 .

7.1 Tensile Testing

Tensile testing has been performed on the specimens in accordance with Indian Standard. The rectangular specimen is of 14 mm x 24.5 mm cross-section, overall length = 270 mm, and gauge length = 168 mm. The specimen sustained a maximum load of 560 kg (5600 N) and underwent an elongation of 0.75 mm. The observations are taken at load interval of 40 kg. Thus the ultimate strength is calculated as 228.5 kg/cm^2 (22.8 MPa), linear strain = 3550×10^{-6} , and lateral strain = 3710×10^{-6} . The stress-strain curve is shown in Fig 6.

7.2 Compression Test

This test has been performed on the U/D hybrid specimen on UTM. The specimen used is of 25 mm x 25 mm cross-section and 30 mm height. The specimen sustained a maximum load of 3.5 tonnes before fracture, where the contraction recorded is 0.16 mm. Thus the ultimate strength is found to be 560 kg/cm^2 (56.0 MPa) and strain = 3100×10^{-6} . The stress-strain diagram is shown in Fig. 7.

7.3 Bending Test

This test has been performed on a U/D specimen of 270 mm span, 20 mm x 14 mm cross-section, simply supported, and subjected to a concentrated mid-span load. The flexure strength is found to be 361.6 MPa. Maximum deflection is recorded as 3.5 mm under a load of 350 kg (3500N). The load-deflection curve is shown in Fig. 8.

7.4 Impact Test

The Charpy and Izod tests have been performed on U/D specimens of width = 10 mm and thickness = 30 mm, having depth of v-notch = 2 mm. The length of specimen in Charpy test is 50 mm, while in Izod test it is 75 mm. The impact strength in Charpy test is found to be 57 kgm (570 Nm), while in Izod test it is 21 kgm (210 Nm).

8. SUMMARY OF RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

From the above experimental observations, the following results given in Table 1 are obtained for different material systems.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of FFRC, GRP, FGFH and GFGH

Properties ↓ Type of Composites/ hybrids →	FFRC	GRP	FGFH	GFGH
Density (kg/m ³)	1648.0	1898.0	1880.0	1940.0
Tensile strength (MPa)	31.2	33.3	18.6	22.8
Compressive strength (MPa)	32.0	31.2	51.2	56.0
Flexure strength (MPa)	40.8 (with 1- ply)	48.2 (with 1- ply)	309.9 (with 3- ply)	361.6 (with 3- ply)
Impact strength (Nm) : Charpy : Izod	8.8	120.0	480.0	570.0
	3.9	-	160.0	210.0
Specific tensile strength (MPa/ kg/m ³)	0.0189	0.0175	0.0098	0.011

It is clearly evident that the effect of hybridization is to enhance the compressive strength, flexural strength and impact strength as compared to non-hybrid composites. However, the tensile strength lowers down. Further, the effect of different stacking sequence of dual fibre composite is to improve all the properties as compared to non-hybrid composite. It is also concluded that the stacking configuration of GFGH is better than the stacking configuration of FGFH in all respects. It results in the following improvements.

- Increase in tensile strength = 18.4%
- Increase in compressive strength = 8.5%
- Increase in flexural strength = 14.2%
- Increase in impact strength = 15.7%
- Increase in specific tensile strength = 10.9%

Hence it is concluded that 'GFGH' will prove to be a better material for applications such as supports, lightweight machines and equipment, vivid structural elements; for low pressure applications such as pipes carrying sewage and industrial waste; low strength applications such as tables, boards, supporting pads etc.

References

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